

The Social Work Attitude Test for Students (SWATS-15)

Item no.	Item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1.	The poor deserve to be treated with respect, just like the rich.					
2.	The old deserve to live with dignity, even if they are unable to work.					
3.	Labourers deserve to be treated with dignity and respect.					
4.	Everyone must be allowed to express their thoughts about a law.					
5.	People must never use insulting language on social media.					
6.	We must preserve the environment for future generations.					
7.	The government must provide food, shelter, and clothing to the poor.					
8.	It's important to respect colleagues at work.					
9.	People must be allowed to keep their private lives confidential.					
10.	Old people shouldn't be allowed to vote.					
11.	People must be free to decide whether they want to have children.					
12.	As a professional, one must reach the office on time.					
13.	People who are mentally ill are a burden to society.					

14.	Corruption is acceptable under some circumstances.					
15.	Sports are only for people who don't have a disability.					

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